

ENERGY EFFICIENT CLUSTERING TECHNIQUE TO REDUCE LOAD IN CLOUD COMPUTING

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Abstract: For provisioning of various computing resources in recent days cloud computing data centers are becoming popular. Now reducing of energy consumption is the main issues at different data centers. In the field of Cloud Computing Clustering technique is the best technique to reduce the load at data centers and finally energy consumption will be reduced. In this paper, energy efficiency with reducing load is the main issue and to reduce the load at different data centers different energy efficiency and load balancing techniques implemented.

Keywords: Load Balancing, Clustering, Energy Consumption, Cloud Computing

Introduction: Cloud Computing is network of computers connected to each other with internet and shared resources. Recourses can be any type of resources like Hardware, Application, Services, Server, Processing Power, Memory, Operating System, Network etc...

A cloud word shows the internet and computing is a process of utilizing computer technology to complete our task. The two important concepts in the “cloud” are:

1. Abstraction [14]: From users and developers the information of system implementation is abstracted in cloud computing. On unknown addresses data is saved, on unspecified physical system applications run and also system administration is provided to others. Therefore, on unspecified physical system all the applications run, on unknown address data is saved, system administration is outsourced to others and finally it is accessed by users.
2. Virtualization [10]: By pooling and resource sharing Cloud computing virtualizes systems. Systems and storage can be provisioned as needed from a centralized infrastructure, costs are assessed on a metered basis, multi-tenancy is enabled, and resources are scalable with agility. By creating virtual version of any device or any resource and dividing framework in executable environment virtualization can be achieved. Electricity can be an example of virtualization, where it is coming from substation and distributed to different location and same time. Cloud Computing is on demand computing services initially offered by commercial provides such as Amazon, Google and Microsoft.

This model aim is to provide resources as services which can be used or accessed from anywhere and anytime.

As per NIST “Cloud Computing [12] is a model for having omnipresent, suitable, whenever required network access to shared pool with so many computing assets which are

configurable like (Network, Server, Storage, Application and Services) which can be fast equipped and then can be released with least control efforts or providers communication”.

Explain Layer Architecture of cloud computing: -

According to level of abstraction of the capability and provided service model Cloud computing services are divided into three classes, namely:

1. Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS)
2. Platform as a Service (PaaS)
3. Software as a Service (SaaS)

Services of higher level can be composed from underlying in abstraction level.

● Infrastructure as a Service:

- Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) [1,2,4,12,13] is popular for providing on demand virtual resources.
- Several options of operating system and software stack with customization is available for on demand provisioning of servers. Such services are observed as the bottom layer of cloud computing.
- IaaS mainly offers Amazon Web Services which in the case of its EC2service which means it is offering VMs with the help of a software stack that can be customized similar to how an ordinary physical server can be customized.
- Various privileges for performing activity to the server like starting and stopping, installing software packages and customizing it, virtual disks are given to users.

Figure 1: Layered Architecture of Cloud Service Model

Platform as a Service:

- Platform as a Service (PaaS) [1,2,4,12,13] means higher level of abstraction which help cloud easily programmable.
- An environment where developers create and deploy applications and also don't need to know about the processors and memory will be using is offered by a cloud platform offers.
- Specialized services like data access, authentication and payments are offered as building blocks to new applications.
- It offers environment for developing and hosting web applications which can be written in specific language like python or Java. Google App Engine, an example of Platform as a Service.

Software as a Service:

- With the help of Web portals end users can use services provided by this layer. Applications reside on the top of the cloud stack. From locally installed computer programs now consumers are shifting to online services.
- As a service in web can be used to access traditional desktop applications such as word processing and spreadsheet. This model of delivering applications, known as Software as a Service (SaaS) [1,2,4,12,13].

Problem Statement: In cloud data centers Methods and standards are needed to benchmark the energy efficiency of cloud services at IaaS, PaaS and SaaS [1,2,4,12,13] levels. The use of software defined infrastructures and the associated protocols, tools, and models allow new levels of flexibility in clouds and new multi-objective optimization models are needed to trade-off between performance levels, energy efficiency [5,7,9], and cost. New intelligent deployment and runtime optimization approaches are needed to take into account the energy consumed considering the user demand patterns. Some Applications are only used during day-time, others during the weekend and algorithms need to be developed to predict the behavior of the different applications deployed in the cloud. Virtual infrastructure can be re-deployed at runtime in cloud infrastructures to minimize the Number of physical machines being used and to switch off unused machines to reduce both Costs and energy consumed.

Many research papers already published for save energy and for reduce load [2,3,4,6] in cloud. When system in ideal state then we can save energy and also save energy when system in working state. Lots of user working at that time then load is producing so that system works slow down. That's way we can reduce load in cloud computing data centers.

Lots of algorithms available for save energy and for reduce load [2,3,4,6] in cloud. but they can save very less energy we can try to save more energy and try to reduce load in cloud computing using only algorithm.

Existing and proposed work: Different research paper

available for reduce energy efficient [5,7,9]. It reduces load over network and efficient the energy in terms of saving using different algorithms and different technique and also uses different tools. But they can 10% to 15% energy save only.

I can try to save more energy in my project and try to reduce load [2,3,4,6] also using different algorithms and different technique.

Figure 2: Flow of Control

Figure 3: Proposed Architecture

Using above parameter, we will implement our new algorithm and make cloud energy more efficient and also reduce load in cloud computing.

Proposed Algorithm:

In past research work, many research papers available for reducing load and energy efficiency. Most of the algorithm reduces load and in terms of energy it is efficient using different algorithms and different technique using different tools. But they can save 10% to 15% energy only. The proposed algorithm can save more energy in cloud datacenter and reduce load using different algorithms and different technique.

Here one algorithm has implemented for load reduction, carbon footprint reduction and save more energy in cloud computing.

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